

BIOLOGICAL WEAPONS AND EMERGING PUBLIC HEALTH CONCERNS

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Abstract

The world is facing the growing threat of biological weapons which can be used for biological warfare or bioterrorism. The issue is of great concern as the biological weapons can not only be easily acquired and produced at a mass level but also because they can cause mass casualties. History has shown that biological weapons have been used over different period of times such as the use of smallpox by the European colonizers in the American continent to achieve the desired results of conquest. Evidence has also shown that some countries involved in World War I, II, during the Cold war period and even after the end of the Cold war to some extent had developed secret Biological Weapons programmes. The objective was to infect the enemy. The terrorist incidents in the United States and in the other parts of the world which involved bacterial pathogens, also showed that all nations today, equally face the threat of biological and chemical weapons.

Understanding the intensity of the threats and the public health concerns involved, initiatives have been taken to prohibit the development, production, stockpiling, and use of biological weapons at the international level. However, the efforts are not without its challenges such as misuse of biological research, adherence to universal compliances etc. The need therefore arises to understand the gravity of the threat and to overcome the challenges faced.

The research paper therefore focusses on the various threats to public health arising because of biological weapons and seeks to analyse the efforts made at the international level to contain them.

Keywords: *Biological Weapons, Bioterrorism, Agro-bioterrorism, Threats, Public Health, International Treaties.*

INTRODUCTION:

Technology holds the promise of development and a great future but it is like a double-edged sword for it can be used in a manner which can bring disastrous effects not only for humans

but for all living and non-living entities. Innovations in biotechnology have brought its benefits in the health, food, environment, research as well as in many other areas, however, it has also sowed the seeds of unprecedented devastation by developing biological warfare agents known as 'Biological Weapons.'

Biological Weapons refer to munitions, equipment or other means of delivery including bombs, aircraft spray tanks and other devices, intended for use in the dissemination of biological agents and toxins for hostile purposes.¹ The use of these agents and instruments to spread terror is known as 'Bioterrorism.'

The World Health Organisation (WHO) has defined biological-warfare agents as 'ones that depend for their effects on multiplication within the target organism and that are intended for use in war to cause disease or death in man, animals or plants, they may be transmissible or non-transmissible.'²

Biological warfare thus refers to the military employment of biological agents such as bacteria, viruses, fungi or toxins that exist in nature to produce the desired results such as death, temporary incapacitation, or permanent harm in human, animals or plants life.³ It is also done with the intention to disrupt the society, and to damage the economy. As some of these agents are also transmissible, they may cause adverse effects to those infected.⁴ The type of bioweapons which can be used for biological warfare are - Anthrax, Aflatoxin, Botulinum Toxin, Ebola-influenza hybrid, Plague, Q-fever, Ricin, RNA, Saxitoxin, Smallpox, Substance P, Tularemia.⁵

The intentional use of biological weapons has occurred sporadically for centuries. Few of the earliest recorded cases are the use of smallpox virus infected blankets by the British Army in 1763 to spread the epidemic in an American Indian tribe.⁶ In 1856 in the Crimean port of 'Kaffa' the plague infected corpses were catapulted by the besieging Tartar armies in the enemy

¹ Guillemin Jeanne, *Biological Weapons, From the Invention of State-Sponsored programs to Contemporary Bioterrorism*, Columbia University Press, New York, 2005, p.2

² Goldblat Jozef, *The Biological Weapons Convention An overview*, International Review of the Red Cross, <https://international-review.icrc.org/> p. 253

³ Guillemin Jeanne, *Op. Cit.*, p. 2

⁴ *Biological Attack Fact Sheet: Human Pathogens, Biotoxins, and Agricultural Threats*, Biological Attack Fact Sheet, Homeland Security, <https://www.dhs.gov/publication/biological-attack-fact-sheet/>

⁵ Mishra R. C., *Terrorism – Implications of Tactics and Technology*, Authorspress Pub., 2004, pp. 110-111

⁶ Guillemin Jeanne, *Op. Cit.*, p.3

city walls thereby spreading plague. The Genoese defenders on contracting plague fled to Italy spreading the disease to Europe which resulted in 'Black Death' and wiped out nearly one-third of the European population.⁷

Evidence also suggests that during World War I Germany, developed ambitious biological warfare programme. It made use of anthrax and glanders to infect the cavalry horses in the United States and France, sheep in Romania, and livestock in Argentina.

During the Second World War, the United States and Canada secretly tried to develop an anti-livestock bioweapon 'rinderpest' (highly lethal disease of cattle.) Between 1951 and 1969 also, the stem rust of wheat, rye, and rice blast, three anti-crop agents were produced and stockpiled by the United States.⁸

From 1960 to early 1990s, the 'Ekologiya' project, was pursued by the USSR to inflict enormous damage on Western agriculture. It was considered to be the world's biggest project for the destruction of agriculture as the Soviet Union had developed anti-crop and anti-livestock weapons.⁹

During the 1980's Iran-Iraq War, a variety of fungal agents were developed by Iraq to attack Iran's staple food crops. Further, to demonstrate the effectiveness of an anti-crop agent, field tests of wheat cover smut were conducted by the Iraqi government in 1985 and 1988. Canisters were also produced and designed by Iraq to infect the Iranian wheat fields.¹⁰

During the period of World War II, the United States, Britain, Canada, Japan and some of the European countries engaged in the research and development of biological weapons. Evidence suggests the use of biological weapons by Japan on the people and prisoners in China. France was also producing an anti-crop program to target Germany.¹¹

The Sverdlovsk Anthrax Outbreak (1979) caused at least 66 deaths as there was an accidental release of anthrax spores from a Soviet's Sverdlovsk bio-weapons facility. Critical information on aerosolized anthrax dispersal and human susceptibility was provided by the incident.¹² This

⁷ Mishra R. C., Op. Cit., p. 107

⁸ Biowarfare Against Agriculture, Case Studies in Agricultural BioSecurity, <https://biosecurity.fas.org/>

⁹ Ibid.

¹⁰ Ibid.

¹¹ Uppal Rajesh, Remerging threat of Biological Weapons attack against Agricultural Targets and Agrobioterrorism, with advances in Gene editing, synthetic biology, and improved delivery systems, IDST, March 6, 2021, <https://idstch.com/threats/>

¹² Dr. Shatdhar Sanjay S., Dr. Bhargava Sameer, The Effects of Biological Weapons on Human Health: A Comprehensive Review, Amoghvarta, December 2023 to February 2024, Copyright © 2025, *Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies*

century also witnessed the conduct of biological weapons experiments on prisoners of war and civilians.

Further, from 1901 to 2000, the world is also said to have witnessed an increase use of scientific developments in microbiology for its use in warfare such as the US anthrax incident of 2001.¹³ Today the international security is still therefore significantly plagued by the possibility of such applications and it has emerged as a rising international concern.

POTENTIAL THREAT:

The Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) defines three categories of biological agents which have the potential to be used as weapons. It is based on the ease of dissemination or transmission, potential for major public health impact, potential for creating public panic, social disruption, as well as requirements for public health preparedness. Agents of highest concern are *Bacillus anthracis*, *Yersinia pestis*, *Variola major*, *Clostridium botulinum* toxin, *Francisella tularensis*, Filoviruses and Arenaviruses.¹⁴

Concerns are raised as biological weapons are easy to proliferate and use. The footprints required to move and use them are also less as compared to the other weapons of mass destruction. They are easy to manufacture as its resources, are more accessible and less expensive. Many agents required to produce bioweapons are also used for medical purposes. Further, the technology required to produce them is available for civilian and military purposes. Bioweapons thus are less visible, highly potential, largely accessible, and also relatively easy to deliver. For example, a millionth of a gram of anthrax can be a highly lethal dose. Under ideal conditions, a kilogram of anthrax has the potential to kill hundreds of thousands of people.¹⁵

According to the World Health Organization ‘the potential threat from aerosol clouds is evident from an estimate that 50 kilograms of dry anthrax used against a city of one million people would kill 36,000 people and incapacitate around 54,000 people. Further the technology needed for aerosol dissemination is also commercially available.’¹⁶

Volume-03, Issue-03, p. 268

¹³ Mishra R. C., Op. Cit., p.108

¹⁴ Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report, October 19, 2001, <https://www.cdc.gov/mmwr/preview/>

¹⁵ Mishra R. C., Op. Cit., p. 119

¹⁶ W. Seth Carus, The threat of bioterrorism, Strategic Forum, National Defense University, Institute for National Strategic Studies, Number 127, September 1997, p.1

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The US anthrax incidents in 2001 also highlighted to the world the dangers posed by intentional anthrax deployment as, it resulted in the loss of several lives and widespread public fear. Inhalational anthrax is highly lethal as the mortality rate can be 100% unless it is treated immediately. Further, though smallpox was eradicated from the entire world through vaccination, its potential use as a biological weapon is still a matter of concern as, if the virus is used as a weapon as it can cause an outbreak. The impact will be disastrous, and more people may die or get seriously ill within the unvaccinated populations.

Botulinum Toxin (*Clostridium botulinum* toxin) which can disrupt nerve function is also one of the most potent toxins known to humans and its use in bioterrorism or biological warfare is of great concern due to its high lethality and potential for large-scale impact.¹⁷ Epidemics can also be started by biological agents which are capable of secondary transmission.

Biological weapons are also a grave threat as their attack may be similar to a natural occurring event and may therefore complicate the assessment and response of the public health officials. As the effects of use of biological weapons also takes time, it would also become difficult to detect it in the earlier stages.¹⁸

Further, there is a growing fear that during any war or conflict, laboratories working on highly potential pathogens can be attacked which can lead to serious public health consequences. Similarly, the assessment of the effect of the attack may also take time due to its covert release which sometimes may resemble the naturally occurring outbreaks. Many countries have also developed biowarfare programs to target crops and farm animals. The aim is to deny food, cause economic damage and lower public morale of the target enemy country. This can lead to serious social and economic consequences such as profound dislocation, loss of agricultural crops, animals, markets, inflation, unemployment etc. There is also a possibility that in a country a foreign disease may not only infect local people, plant or animal life but it may get permanently entrenched.¹⁹

Concerns are thus raised that with the developments in technology, biological weapons could be developed or used by not only States, but can be acquired, produced or used by non-state actors also, resulting in serious consequences for the entire world.²⁰

¹⁷ Dr. Shatdhar Sanjay S., Dr. Bhargava Sameer, Op. Cit., p. 267

¹⁸ Filder David P., Gostin Lawrence O., Bio Security in the Global Age, Biological Weapons, Public Health, and The Rule of Law, Stanford University Press, 2008, p. 26

¹⁹ Ibid., p. 24

²⁰ Biological Weapons, <https://disarmament.unoda.org/>

The use of biological agents for biowarfare is thus a matter of serious concern.

EFFECTS/IMPACT:

The use of biological weapons results in physical, psychosocial and societal impact. Along with direct health consequences, the psychosocial impact extends to the fear of contagion, isolation, and death which can lead to widespread panic and societal disruption. Social problems may emerge such as displacement of people, breakdown of community support systems, divisions in the society and social stigma faced by infected people due to contagion or contamination. Significant anxiety and mistrust, was witnessed within the affected communities of the United States after the anthrax letter attacks of 2001.²¹

Physical exposure to the biological warfare agents may lead to organic mental disorders such as organic psychosis, delirium, dementia etc. Various long-term social and mental problems may be experienced when exposed to any severe stressor such as anxiety, mood disorders as well as non-pathological trauma and grief reactions.

The fear of biological and chemical attacks may also result in medically unexplained illness as invisible agents may be involved.²² The feeling of helplessness is increased and experienced when the agent is easily communicable as health workers, family, friends, and neighbours may be sources of illness. This would also result in unavailability of safe health care and social support system when needed the most.

Further, lack of information and clarity may also be faced as many of the biological agents have not been encountered earlier. Professionals may not be able to identify the people who are at risk, those infected and the effects. This would create hurdles in managing the crisis.

People may also confuse their body signs of autonomic arousal as signs of infection which may further put pressure on the health services.

Health issues will also be faced by persons especially the service providers who will have to wear protective gear such as clothes, masks, and respirators. They may experience issues related to heat, breathing, claustrophobic effects, verbal communication, and reduced performance of task considered necessary for survival.²³

²¹ Dr. Shatdhar Sanjay S., Dr. Bhargava Sameer, Op. Cit., p. 268

²² Mental Health of Populations Exposed to Biological and Chemical Weapons, World Health Organization Geneva, 2005, p. 2, <https://iris.who.int/>

²³ Ibid., p.3

PREVENTIVE MEASURES:

Treaties have been signed at the international level to forbid the development, production and use of biological and chemical weapons to which most states are signatories such as the Geneva Protocol (1925) prohibited the use of Asphyxiating, Poisonous or Other Gases, and of Bacteriological Methods of Warfare.²⁴

The 1972 Biological and Toxin Weapons Convention (BWC) prohibits the Development, Production and Stockpiling of Biological and Toxin Weapons and on their Destruction.²⁵ The treaty banned all category of weapons of mass destruction (WMD).

Resolutions 1540 and 2325 adopted by the United Nations Security Council puts obligation on all states to prevent the proliferation of nuclear, biological and chemical weapons to non-State actors. The members of parliaments are also under obligation to see that the resolutions are implemented by their respective governments.²⁶

To deal with the crisis arising due to biological attack and to mitigate the consequences the World Health Organisation (WHO) also works with the affected State or States or any international body and provides advise on strengthening of their public health surveillance and response systems.²⁷ Measures such as improved biosafety, biosecurity and communication system across different public service agencies will also be provided throughout the health sector. In case of the deliberate use of biological agents with the intention to cause harm, efforts would also be made to deal with its psychological and social consequences. Contingency plans would be implemented to overcome it by all sectors.²⁸

The 'Australia Group' which is an informal forum of industrialized countries has also been formed to reduce the risk of misuse of biological weapons. Certain restrictions have been applied by the group on transfers of items relevant to the Biological Weapons Convention.²⁹

²⁴ Protocol for the Prohibition of the use of Asphyxiating, Poisonous or Other Gases and of Bacteriological Methods of Warfare, Geneva, 17 June 1925, International Humanitarian Law Databases, <https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/>

²⁵ Convention on the Prohibition of Biological Weapons, International Humanitarian Law Databases, <https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/>

²⁶ Chemical and Biological Weapons, Assuring our Common Future, <https://disarmamenthandbook.org/>

²⁷ Biological weapons, <https://www.who.int/health>

²⁸ Ibid.

²⁹ Goldblat Jozef, Op. Cit., p. 255

CONCLUSION:

Today public health can no longer be separated from security. There is a need to include threats from infectious disease in public health infrastructure as diseases caused by such weapons are not restricted to national borders. It can spread rapidly around the world bringing disastrous consequences.

The Research and Development in offensive and defensive biological weapons, can also raise suspicion which can lead to a new biological arms race. Further, all nations have not agreed to participate in the efforts taken at the international level to prohibit the development, production and use of biological and chemical weapons. Hence, the concerns remain that some countries as well as non-state entities may try to gain access and may resort to the use of these weapons. Finally, as it may not be possible to always prevent the attack of biological weapons, resulting in devastating consequences, constant vigilance and focussed efforts of domestic and international law enforcement agencies as well as enlightened people's participation will be required to prevent it as well as to overcome it.

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